

CREATIVE IMPLEMENTATION MODEL OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

(This creative model has made Gresik regency as the Leading of Inclusive Education in Indonesia and awarded an Inclusive Education Award)

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Abstract: *Inclusive Education, an ideology based on the new education philosophy which is humane, democratic, and non-discriminatory and for all. All the government systems in Gresik regency are very care to the Inclusive Education. Because of that, this great practical education should be socialized in order to motivate other country in implementation of Inclusive education. By using the creative model in the implementation of Inclusive Education, it can be proven by the Increasing of the pure participation number of children with special need about 131,6 percents and leading Gresik Regency awarded an inclusive Education award from National Education Ministry.*

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive Education is a new ideology based on the educational philosophy of humane, democratic, non-discriminatory and for all. Inclusive Education Policy is applied in line with the Statement of International Education (EFA) by the UNESCO. It means that education is a human right. Therefore all people have to get an education, it means there is no exception included who were marginalized or the people who have not received education or who have served education the form of segregated from society.

In Indonesia, the policy on inclusive education as stated by EFA, in accordance with Article 31 of the Constitution of 1945, paragraph (1) that:

"Setiap warga negara berhak mendapatkan pendidikan" dan ayat (2): "Setiap warga negara wajib mengikuti pendidikan dasar dan pemerintah wajib membiayainya".

It means:

"Every citizen has an education right" and paragraph (2): "Every citizen is obliged to participate in primary education and the government is obliged to finance it."

This Article is as a basic legal law to make a policy of Education for All (EFA) and it is stated on National Education System No 20/2003 article 5 (1) that: "Every citizen has the same rights to get quality education."

Based on the explanation of education for all, the government has to be responsible for the implementation of inclusive education in Indonesia. The policies are (1) Basic education quality and (2) Basic education is free for all. Inclusive education that applied Education for all also strengthened on minister of national education regulation no. 70 of 2009.

It is stated: *"Pendidikan Inklusif didefinisikan sebagai sistem penyelenggaraan pendidikan yang memberikan kesempatan kepada semua peserta didik yang memiliki kelainan dan memiliki potensi kecerdasan dan atau bakat istimewa untuk mengikuti*

pendidikan atau pembelajaran dalam lingkungan pendidikan secara bersama-sama dengan peserta didik pada umumnya. (Permendiknas No.70, 2009:1)

In the implementation of minister national education regulation no. 70 of 2009, there are two types service in formal education system in Indonesia. First, inclusive education that supports for children with potential special needs-gifted and talented children (CIBI) and second, inclusive education that supports for Children with Special Need (disabilities children).

Gifted and talented students get education services at general inclusive school such as Supecial Schools / Favorite School / Reference School and fillow accelerated program or Olympiad class program so all gifted and talented students have to get quality education based on their need, While students with special needs who have barriers and handicapped are served in inclusive schools. These schools location are close with their homes.

The latest development, according to Law number 8/2016 about disability states that education services for disability people has been implemented by two ways, special education and inclusive education. According to Law number 23/2014, the authority of special education and inclusive education for high school / vocational school is the province authority, while the Inclusive Education policy for basic education level is the responsibility of local government. Thus all the leaders are expected to have commitment to pay attention to education for children with special needs.

Gresik Government welcomed the new policy and managed strategies of its implementation. Even it often got obstacles in implementing inclusive education with a variety of reasons. Implementation Inclusive education is necessary. Based on data collection in 2016, the numbers of children with special needs (ABK) in Gresik are 1936 children. The reality is 925 (47%) who does not have education services. Therefore, we need creative strategies for

accelerating the implementation of inclusive education. It is suitable with the vision of Gresik Regency- religious fair, prosperous and living quality.

OBJECTIVE

The implementation strategy of Inclusive Education in Gresik, East Java, Indonesia is different from the other provinces. Therefore the best practice has to be disseminated in order to motivate other countries.

Description of Implementation

Implementation of Inclusive Education in Gresik is supported by the Head of Gresik regency regulation no. 42/2013 about Inclusive Education and regulation no. 12/2012 about Unit Resource Center as capacity maintenance of inclusive education, socialization, publications on print media, radio, television and online. There is also an instruction from the Head of Gresik Regency no: 421/4457 / 437.53 / 2013 about the implementation of inclusive education in all schools.

Capacity building through training or workshop, shortcuts to Western Australia and Flinders University, Hearing and Communications Center (HCC) and the Autism Association of Western Australia (AAWA), the Special Education Teacher (GPK) have to follow the KTT program (Competence and authority Supplement) at Surabaya State University, as well as a comparative study.

Developing network and having partnerships with Indonesia University and abroad such as State University of Surabaya, Muhammadiyah University of Gresik, Airlangga University and Flinders University in Australia, HCC, AAWA, dr. Soetomo Hospital, Ibn Sina Hospital, Bureau of International Cooperation Province Government of East Java, the Department of Health, Social Services, Department of Labor, Department of Public Works, Department of Public Planning and Department of Child Protection, the PKK, Darmawanita, Health Centers and Polyclinics.

In order to increase educational services, the local government has established Resource Center, allocated special funding for Renovation of Resource Center building, Government Budgeting (BOSDA), and gave incentives for special education teachers, School Inclusion Assistance and training. The purpose of the effort is to increase the students with special needs enrollment rate in basic education and also support the achievement of the MDG's.

One of the creative and innovative in the implementations of inclusive education in Gresik is institutional support. Gresik Government has a policy that resource centers as institutions for technical unit (UPT) to support the implementation of inclusive education, this policy stated on the Head of Gresik regency regulation no12/2012. The resource center as information and consultation center, the assessment and early detection place of intervention services and therapy as well as giving recommendations for

children with special need to go to higher school level. Resource Center also serves as a center of research and development of inclusive education, Teachers, principals and parents Center, and as a class transition.

Based on the research and experience of managing special education, having Resource Center to support the implementation of inclusive education in district / city is very important. All districts / cities don't have a special School as resource center. The reason is the number of teachers in special schools is limited. Teachers have skills to handle one type of barrier or impairment. Another reason is the place of PLA (autism service center) at province area. The distance is very far so the people who lived far away or in a remote area, poor families or busy parents cannot go to get services.

Therefore Gresik government has established a Resource Center. The resource center provides free of charge, good quality and public services. It is supported by official and staff of hearing and Communications Center (HCC) and the Autism Association of Western Australia (AWA). This program was a collaboration program with Western Australia Patricia O'Sullivan and NGO International Humanitarian Project (POSH).

The Advantages of Inclusive Educations A Culture

Both Gresik Government and Special Education Directorate have commitment to improve regional services for the children with special need. Special Education Directorate has selected the best districts and gave funding of inclusive education culturally program. The impact of inclusive education culturally program and launching of an inclusive award is great in acceptance and understanding of the inclusive education in Gresik from public, Business and Industry, Office of cross-sector, principal, supervisor, and head of Unit, Community leaders and others.

All of this support is strengthened by Head of Gresik regency regulation such as BOSDA for children with special need at Special School and Inclusive School. Elementary and Junior High School Students are given Rp. 115.000 / student / month and Senior High School and vocational students are given Rp.150.000 / student / month. Special Education teachers are given Rp. 250.000 /person/month, The Resource Center trainees followed short course in Australia for 6 weeks, Special Education Teachers studied at Surabaya State University, and the best Special Education Teachers got scholarship to take the Master of Special Education at Surabaya State University with a scholarship.

Business, Industry and the community participate to help the students with special need. Support Teachers from public school have trained to improve their competence to understand the implementation of inclusive education, such as workshops or training, monitoring and evaluation and

improve quality services from the West Australian Government, and free service in Resource Center.

Funding Source

The funding of inclusive education implementation in Gresik Regency is covered from Regional Government Budget (APBD), Regional Government Budget I (APBD I), National Government Budget (APBN), Business and Industry, Society, national and international benefactors.

Results and Impact Of Community

Since Gresik District Government issued a special policy to support the acceleration of the implementation of inclusive education, at the moment, the society has a strong commitment to improve the service and assistance, the society has

acceptance and understanding of inclusive education. Parents of Children with Special Needs have commitment, consult and participate in therapy program at the Resource Center. They appear to be happy and no longer feel ashamed to have children with special needs.

Other impacts of many Public schools have reported their students who had special need and asked to get services, The latest data of the development of Inclusion School in the academic year 2015/2016 shows: the number of inclusion schools in Gresik are 130 institutions, and the number of Children with Special Needs who attend the Inclusion School are 533 students and 625 students who attend at Special, other children are still aged under five.

The Difference Situation before the Initiative and After The Initiative

NO	THE DIFFERENT ASPECTS	BEFORE	AFTER
1.	Inclusive Education Working Group	not yet created	Created Head of Gresik Regency Regulation no.1147/HK/437.12/2013
2	Regulation	Head of Gresik Regency Regulation about the policy of 21 Inclusive School	- The Head of Gresik Regency Regulation no 12/2012 about UPT Resource Centre - The Head of Gresik Regency Regulation no42/2013 about Inclusive Education - SK no.421/4457/437.53/2013 about all schools are obliged to be inclusive schools - A Grand Design of Developing Inclusive - SK about extra duties of the supervisor - SK Inclusive Support Teacher - SK Extra Duties of Trainee Resource - SK The Head of Resource Centre - SK Special School as Sub Resource Center - SK Piloting School Inclusive
3	Socialization and Publication	Not yet	Created printed media, online, electronic media, on air, Television, competitions, talk show, banner, and other information boards and flyers.
4	Capacity Building	Teacher Training	meetings, Training / Workshop of teachers / Principals / Supervisors / Working Groups / Stakeholders, UNESA faculty assistance, class management Assistance, management agencies and special service programs, send Trainee Resource to dr. Soetomo hospital, Western Australia, Comparative Study to Australia West, send teachers to flinders University, scholarship, Special Teacher's KKT Program.
5	Increased Commitment	Not yet	School Inclusion Exhibition, Comparative Study to School Model and PLA, talk show, MOU with Surabaya Stated University / Flinders University / POSH Western Australia
6	Collaboration and Partnership	Not yet	(Heath Department, Social Department, Disnaker) regent / province, business and industry, Higher Education, Ibnu Sina Hospital, RS dr. Soetomo hospital, RSP UNAIR, Directorate, East Java Provincial Overseas Cooperation Administration Bureau, and Western Australian Government
7	Inclusive School Piloting	Not yet	In 2013: SDN Mriyunan Sidayu, SDN Tlogo Patut I Gresik, SMPN 4 Gresik.

8	Resource Center	Not yet	In 2014 : SDN Sidokumpul 7 Gresik, dan SMPN 3 Sidayu Resource Centre supported 7 Special Education Schools sub resource center
9.	Children with Special Need data collection	Not yet	Done. Collaboration with all elements of society, Health Department, Health Center, integrative service post, PKK, GOW, community leaders, Special Education Teachers, Trainee Resource Center
10	Inclusive Regency Declaration	Not yet	Done 9 September 2013 attended 4.000 people from all element of society Regent, province and national.
11	Funding	Rp. 300.000.000 Regional Government Budget	APBD (Regional Government Budgeting) Resource center building renovation, Inclusive school Assistance, Supporting teachers workshop, Special Government Budgeting) around Rp. 2 Billion). Beneficial Funding for Supporting teacher incentive Rp.80.000.000, Business and Industry such as Petrokimia dan Smelting around Rp. 300.000.000, Regional Government Budgeting I Rp. 100.000.000, second APBN Rp. 900.000.000. Total amount Rp.3.380.000.000,00
12	Monitoring evaluating and reporting	None	Internal: Monitoring and evaluation at piloting school by the vice of the head regent, education service, Work Group of inclusive. External: from the Directorate PPK/LK and Western Australia.
13	Awarding	None	The Pioneer regent of holder of Inclusive Education in Indonesia Inclusive education award 2013
14	Participating Number of ABK at school	500 students	1.158 students (from 1936 students, 533 students goes to inclusive school, 625 at SLB, the others are toddlers)
15	Public Support	None	Supported by all society elements
16	Public Satisfaction	None	Very Satisfied (reporting result)
17	Comparative Study Visit	None	Many visits from local government / The House of Representative Regent / Educational Service/ Leadership Workshop members from around regions in Indonesia/ and The Accesibility of public services(sidewalk)

REFERENCES

- Armstrong, F. 2000. Inclusive Education. London: David Fulton Publisher
- Ashman, A.& Elkins,J,1994. Educating Children With Special Needs. New York: Prentice Hall.
- Bogdan, R.C & Biklen, S, K, 1982. Qualitative Research for Education; An introduction to Theory and Methods. Boston: Allynand Bacon.Inc
- Budiyanto.2011. Best Practices of Inclusive Education in Japan, Australia, India, and Thailand: How to Be Implemented in Indonesia. Unesa Surabaya and Criced Japan : Center for Reseach University of Tsukuba
- Carlberg,C & Kavale ,K. The Efficacy of Special Class vs Regular Class Pplacement for Exceptional children: a Metaanalysis. The Journal of Special Education.14,295
- Colley, H ,2003.Mentoring for Social Inclusion, Kondon : Routledge Falmer
- Creemers, B & Reynolds, D, (ed).1993. School Effectiveness and School Improvement. AnInternasional Journal of Research, Policy and Practice.3". New York :
- Random House Fish,J,1989.What is Spesial Education Philadelphia: Open University Press
- Jaiyarah, Siti, 2013. Conflict Management in implementing Inclusive Education:Desertasi UM
- Loreman, Tim, 2005. Inklusive Education A Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity In the Classroom ; Allen & Unwin Regulation of the Minister of national education the number 70 in 2009 about Inclusive Education For learners who have the disorder and has potential for intelligence and Special Talents Or specific Guidelines for Inclusive Education,Organizing the 2009. Directorate of PSLB
- RI law number. 8 Year 2016 about Disabilities Disability RI number 20 year 2003 about Sistem of National Education. UNESCO ,1994. The Salamanca Statement and Framework For Action on Special Needs Education. PARIS:Author.